

OPTIMIZING THE TRAJECTORY FOR IMPROVING QUALITY EDUCATION USING SLACK-BASED DATA ENVELOPMENT ANALYSIS

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Abstract: *The paper analyzes the performance of sustainable development in thirty-five European countries in the year 2021. SDG 4 – Quality Education – was taken as a benchmark for evaluation. Performance of the countries was evaluated using the Slack-Based Measure Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) model, which has a higher discriminating power than the standard DEA model. Then, stratification of the model was carried out in order to identify several levels of efficiency and reduce the analysis to a partial set of inefficient units. A multi-stage benchmarking method was applied to generate stepwise improvement paths and reveal peer references for inefficient units. The results showed that from the point of view of the effectiveness of national policies for the implementation of SDG 4, the reference countries in 2021 were Belgium, Ireland, Greece, Italy, Luxembourg, Finland, Sweden, Iceland, and Switzerland. Through the process of elimination of efficient states, the optimal benchmarking trajectory was identified using the example of Germany.*

Keywords: *sustainability development goals, quality of education, performance, efficiency, benchmarking, data envelopment analysis, multi-stage evaluation, policy improvement trajectory.*

1. INTRODUCTION

According to the United Nations agenda approved by the General Assembly in 2017, the quality of education - SDG 4 has its quantitative and qualitative dimensions. The quantitative dimension is reflected in the structure of the SDG 4 framework, which consists of two levels with 12 global indicators and 31 thematic indicators, in order to complement the depth and breadth of the global set of indicators (UIS, 2023). The qualitative dimension includes concepts such as inclusion, equality, lifelong learning, international cooperation, etc. Together, these indicators form a multidimensional structure that poses significant methodological challenges for evaluation and cross-country comparison. Hence, the monitoring and follow-up of progress in achieving the goals of SDG 4 and, as a result, the benchmarking of countries, are of key importance for progress in the domain of the national education sector. Achieving the goals set within SDG-4 is of great importance for the achievement of other sustainable development goals (Ferguson & Rooft, 2020; Agbedahin, 2019; Leicht et al., 2018).

In this context, the aim of this paper, on the one hand, is to evaluate the achieved SDG 4 performance through a relative comparison of the observed countries, so that the indicators of the SDG 4 goal, as defined by the European Commission, will be considered as output variables of the Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) model whose mutual influences are also taken into account. On the other hand, although methodologically derived, the actual primary goal is to reach the simplest possible set of the worst states through the multi-stage elimination of efficient states, and in that way, through a reversible process, identify their benchmarking trajectories, as well as the optimal one. Such an approach enables policy makers to identify stepwise improvement scenarios, prioritize achievable benchmarks, and allocate resources more effectively. Chronologically, therefore, the procedure is top - down, that is, it starts from the complete set, and the decision-making process is bottom-up. In this paper, Slack-Based Measure Data Envelopment Analysis was used to calculate the results, which, compared to the standard DEA model (Charnes et al., 1978), has a higher discriminating power and therefore provides a better and more harmonized efficiency calculation. By combining SBM-DEA with a multi-stage stratification mechanism, the methodology also contributes to dynamic benchmarking, offering not just a snapshot but a trajectory for policy improvement.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Assume that there are n decision units, denoted as DMUs. Let DMU_j ($j=1,2,\dots,n$) consume m_1 variable input x_{i_1j} ($i = 1,2,\dots,m_1$) and m_2 fixed input x_{i_2j} ($i = 1,2,\dots,m_2$), to produce k_1 variable output y_{r_1j} ($r_1 = 1,2,\dots,k_1$) and k_2 fixed output y_{r_2j} ($r_2 = 1,2,\dots,k_2$). Then, according to (Tone, 2001), we can evaluate the performance of the observed DMU_0 through the following Slack Based Measure (SBM) input-oriented DEA model (1):

$$h_0 = \frac{1 - \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m \frac{s_i^-}{x_{i_0}}}{1 + \frac{1}{s} \sum_{r=1}^s \frac{s_r^+}{y_{r_0}}} \quad y_{r_0} = \sum_{j=1}^n \lambda_j \times y_{r_j} - s_r^{(+)} \\ s^- \geq 0, s^+ \geq 0 \\ x_{i_0} = \sum_{j=1}^n \lambda_j \times x_{ij} + s_i^{(-)}$$

The optimal solution of model (1) is denoted as $(\theta^*, \lambda_j^*, s_i^{*(-)}, s_r^{*(+)})$. In model (2) the performance of DMU_0 can be improved by $x'_{i_0} = x_{i_0} - s_i^{*(-)}$ and $y'_{r_0} = y_{r_0} + s_r^{*(+)}$, wherein h^* the efficiency of the DMU_0 , λ_j^* contribution of the reference efficient decision-making unit in achieving the goal of the analyzed decision-making unit, and $(x'_{i_0}, \forall i)$ i $(y'_{r_0}, \forall r)$ optimally improved input and output variables, respectively. Unlike radial models, the SBM model measures efficiency by taking into account disproportionate surpluses and deficits of inputs and outputs, which can lead to a more accurate ranking of DMUs, especially when there is an excess of inputs or a deficit of outputs.

3. STRUCTURING OF THE MODEL

The Data Envelopment Analysis has often been used, in different variants, in the measurement and analysis of sustainable development performance (Zhang et al., 2008; Tian et al., 2019; Li et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2018; Long, 2021; Nocera Alvares Junior et al., 2024). The appropriate SBM DEA output oriented model, with two inputs and four outputs are defined as follows:

- 1) A group consisting of thirty-five European countries for which there is available data is observed (Appendix, table A);
- 2) The available data were collected from the *Eurostat* and *World Bank* databases, for the year 2021. The selection of this specific year ensures temporal consistency and comparability across countries, given that 2021 was a post-COVID recovery period with significant implications for education systems.
- 3) Two input variables were chosen: government expenditure on education (% of GDP) and teacher-to-student ratio, reflecting the availability of financial and human resources in the educational system.
- 4) Four output indicators were selected, representing key components of SDG 4 in the EU context, as defined by the European Commission.

The output-oriented SBM DEA model is an adequate and methodologically justified choice in the analysis of the efficiency of educational systems in situations where we want to assess the potential for improving educational results, the data contain disproportionate surpluses and deficits, or we have complex indicators with different directions of desirability (such as SDG4-10). SDG4-10 (early leavers from education and training), measures the percentage of individuals (typically aged 18–24) who have left education and training with at most lower secondary education and are not in further education or training. A high rate suggests challenges in retaining young people in the education system, which can negatively affect employment, economic growth, and social inclusion. So, a lower value for early leavers from education and training is preferable. This is in contrast to standard efficiency measurement in DEA, where a higher output value typically signifies better performance. In order to account for this inverse relationship and maintain consistency with the DEA framework, a multiplicative inversion of the SDG4-10 output value was applied, according to the transformation: $O = 1 / O$. This ensures the model rewards improvements in this indicator appropriately.

The second output refers to the SDG 4.20 indicator – tertiary educational attainment by sex. This indicator measures the share of the population aged 25–34 who have successfully completed tertiary education. It reflects the effectiveness of the education system in enabling young people to attain higher qualifications, which is essential for fostering innovation, competitiveness, and inclusive economic growth.

The third output refers to early childhood education participation by sex, indicating the percentage of children aged three to the start of compulsory primary education who are enrolled in structured early learning programmes (ISCED level 0). These programmes aim to support children's early development, and the EU has set a 2030 target of at least 96% participation, emphasizing the foundational role of early education in lifelong learning.

The fourth output refers to the indicator adult participation in learning in the past four weeks by sex, which tracks the percentage of individuals aged 25 to 64 who reported taking part in formal or non-formal education or training within the four weeks prior to the survey. Adult learning plays a vital role throughout life, supporting professional development, adaptation to new technologies, and reintegration into the labour market, while also contributing to personal well-being, active citizenship, and social inclusion.

The stratification of decision-making units is based on the procedure formulated by Seiford & Zhu, 2003. Let U^l be the set of observed decision-making units, and E^l , the subset of effective decision-making units, so that $E^l \in U^l$. Then the procedure has the following steps:

Step 1: Identification of the set of all decision-making units U^l ;

Step 2: Evaluation of the efficiency of decision units in order to obtain the first level of efficient decision units E^l ;

Step 3: Exclusion of efficient units from the set of DMUs at the first level; $U^{l+1} = U^l - E^l$. If $U^{l+1} = \emptyset$, the procedure stops;

Step 4: Evaluate the new subset of inefficient DMUs, U^{l+1} , in order to obtain a new subset of efficient DMUs, E^{l+1} ;

Step 5: Let $l = l + 1$. Go to step 2.

Stopping rule: $E^{l+1} = \emptyset$, the algorithm stops.

This iterative elimination of efficient units enables a deeper decomposition of inefficiencies and facilitates the construction of benchmarking trajectories for less efficient countries. By applying this procedure, it is possible to determine a multi-stage benchmarking trajectory for inefficient DMUs. In this way, a country can gradually improve its efficiency by benchmarking against a single efficient DMU or a convex combination of efficient DMUs, which overcomes the problem of unrealistic or unfeasible improvement paths (Lim et al., 2011). Such gradual transitions are particularly important in the policy domain, where resource reallocation and systemic reforms are typically incremental rather than immediate.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The process begins with a top-down efficiency evaluation, including all observed decision-making units (DMUs), and gradually identifies optimal benchmarking trajectories starting from the least efficient units. In the first iteration, which consists of a set of 35 observed countries, with two inputs and four output variables, the efficient DMUs are Belgium, Ireland, Greece, Italy, Luxembourg, Finland, Sweden, Iceland, and Switzerland. In the second iteration, the set of decision units was reduced by excluding the efficient countries from the first iteration. Efficient DMUs now include Denmark, Spain, Cyprus, Lithuania, Hungary, Malta, Netherlands, Austria, Romania, Slovenia, Norway, Montenegro, and Serbia. In the third iteration, after excluding efficient DMUs from the second iteration, the reference countries are Estonia, Croatia, Latvia, Portugal, Slovakia, North Macedonia, and Türkiye. Finally, in the fourth iteration, after eliminating all previously identified efficient DMUs, the only remaining inefficient countries are the Czech Republic and Germany. This stage marks the point where the discriminatory power of the DEA model is significantly weakened due to the reduced number of DMUs and a high proportion of efficient units. Therefore, it is the threshold at which further stratification becomes analytically redundant. Germany's efficiency score in the first iteration was only 40.24% of the best practice, revealing considerable inefficiency in its 2021 performance on SDG 4 implementation. Luxembourg was identified as the key reference country contributing most significantly ($\lambda = 1.419$) to the target efficiency for Germany. The data suggest major output-side inefficiencies for Germany, particularly in its teacher-to-student ratio (13.2), which is notably less favorable compared to, for example, Malta (8.7). For example, for sub-goal SDG4-10, while Germany's original value in 2021 was 0.1, the target value to match Luxembourg's efficiency was 0.295, representing an increase of 195.23% (Table 1). For sub-goal SDG4-60, the necessary increase was 229.95%. It is evident that immediate alignment with Luxembourg's level of efficiency is highly unrealistic for Germany in the short term, which underscores the rationale for a step-by-step benchmarking trajectory. Hence, a more feasible solution lies in multi-level benchmarking, allowing for progressive adjustment of output values. In the backward analysis, beginning with the fourth iteration, the reference countries for Germany are France (32.1%) and Poland (77.3%). After adjusting Germany's output variables according to these contributions, the target value of SDG4-60 is recalculated:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Germany } (O_{4SDG\ 4-60}^*) &= \lambda_{France}^* \times O_{4SDG\ 4-60} + \lambda_{Poland}^* \times O_{4SDG\ 4-60} = \\ &= 0.321 \times 11 + 0.774 \times 5.4 = 7.6 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

In a similar way, according to the contributions of the reference countries, in this iteration of France and Poland, the target values of other variables are calculated (Table 5). Now Germany, with the necessary correction of the value of the output variables SDG 4, joins the observed set of decision-making units at level III, so the model is solved anew. The reference country is Portugal, and Germany's efficiency is 58.93% of the reference. After correcting the values of the variables in terms of contribution of France and Poland, Germany becomes efficient in terms of achieving SDG4 progress, after which, with such optimized values of the model variables, it moves to the level corresponding to iteration IV, in the forward analysis. The model is re-solved where the efficiency of Germany is 68.35% of the best practice, and the reference countries in terms of contribution are Latvia (0.106) and Portugal (1.077). The procedure is repeated by correcting the values of the input and output variables for Germany, but now in terms of contributions at this level. These step-by-step corrections form a trajectory that is both methodologically robust and practically attainable, allowing a progressive approach to the optimization of educational performance. The corrected values of the variables for Germany, at all levels in the backward analysis, are shown in Table 6. The optimized values of the variables at this level are now applied to the set of countries in iteration III. The model is solved again, and the German efficiency is now 93.21% of the best practice, and the reference countries are Malta (0.016) and Spain (0.595). Once more, values are corrected based on the contributions of these reference units, and Germany is reinserted into the original full set of DMUs corresponding to the first iteration. By solving the model thus formed, Germany's efficiency is 77.85% of the best practice - a notable improvement compared to the initial 40.24% in the original forward analysis. The reference country is once again Luxembourg, as in the forward analysis, but now the contribution is 0.738 - significantly less than the previous 1.42, demonstrating a less intensive and more realistic path toward alignment with best practice. It is clear that harmonization in order to achieve the targeted efficiency is much more favorable and simpler for Germany when a multi-level benchmarking approach is applied. By correcting the values of the output variables according to the contributions of the reference countries, other inefficient countries also reach the threshold of best practice. Bearing the above in mind, starting from the chronological SBM DEA procedure, the optimal benchmarking trajectory would be to compare and reconcile through the following sequence of reference comparisons:

- France and Poland (Iteration IV)
- Latvia and Portugal (Iteration III)
- Malta and Spain (Iteration II)
- Luxembourg (Iteration I)

with appropriate adjustments to the values of the input and output variables in terms of their contribution. In the final phase, the target values of the output variables, which are necessary for Germany to reach the best practice of the reference countries in 2021, are:

- Government Expenditure to Education = 2.73%
- Teachers/Students Ratio = 6.86%
- SDG 4-10* = 0.154%
- SDG 4-20* = 45.02%
- SDG 4-31* = 65.61%
- SDG 4-60.5* = 13.21%

Table 1: Original and target values of output variables of the model for Germany (forward analysis)

	Expenditure	T/S ratio	SDG 4 -10	SDG 4 -20	SDG 4 - 31	SDG 4 - 60
Original values	5.5	13.2	0.1	37.1	93.1	7.7
Target values	5.25	13.2	0.295	86.58	126.18	25.41
Diff.(%)	-4.52	-	195.23	133.37	35.53	229.95

Table 2: Original and target values of output variables of the model for Germany (backward analysis)

	Expenditure	T/S ratio	SDG 4 -10	SDG 4 -20	SDG 4 - 31	SDG 4 - 60
Original values	5.5	13.2	0.1	37.1	93.1	7.7
II level	5.37	13.22	0.115	47.53	102.07	7.6
III level	3.00	6.86	0.146	30.73	58.50	8.79
IV level	2.73	6.86	0.154	45.02	65.61	13.21
Diff. Target/Original in %	-50.37%	-48.03%	54%	21.35%	-29.53%	71.55%

Table 2 displays the original and optimal values of input and output variables for Germany, optimal in terms of efficiency at all stages of the backward analysis. First, Germany is compared with France and Poland as benchmarks. Based on their contributions shown, it is necessary to adjust the model's variables. At the next level, Latvia and Portugal become the reference countries, with Germany aligning its effectiveness to match their performance. This is followed by benchmarking with Malta and Spain, and finally, Luxembourg. The entire procedure is multi-stage, somewhat slower from a methodological and decision-making standpoint, but offers a significantly higher feasibility of achieving the desired outcomes. It avoids

abrupt reforms or unrealistic targets by providing phased, evidence-based improvement plans tailored to national capacities. In the same way, the optimal benchmarking trajectory for the other inefficient country identified in the forward analysis, the Czech Republic, can be determined. By applying the same reverse DEA model structure and adjusting for its unique variable values, a similarly viable path for SDG4 improvement can be proposed.

5. CONCLUSION

The results of the research indicated a generally high or reference level of efficiency among most European Union member states, with a few notable exceptions. The chosen SBM DEA model is an adequate and methodologically justified choice in the analysis of the efficiency of educational systems, because:

- the goal of the research was the maximization of educational results;
- Policymakers want to know how much educational outcomes can be improved with existing resources - which is exactly what the output-oriented model measures;
- Heterogeneity among countries: The SBM model can accurately capture disproportional ties among indicators and enable a more realistic ranking of countries.

Within the SBM DEA model, which included a set of 35 observed countries, two input variables, and four output indicators, the following countries were identified as efficient Decision Making Units (DMUs) in 2021 in terms of progress toward SDG 4: Belgium, Ireland, Greece, Italy, Luxembourg, Finland, Sweden, Iceland, and Switzerland. The most unexpected result was the low efficiency score of Germany, and to a lesser extent, the United Kingdom, given their economic and institutional strength. However, when considering the actual variable values within the model-such as the student-teacher ratio and specific SDG 4 output metrics - this result becomes less surprising and reveals potential structural weaknesses in their educational systems relative to others. The applied multi-stage benchmarking approach, while conceptually straightforward, is based on the mathematically complex, non-parametric DEA method. By successively eliminating efficient units - first from the complete set and then from reduced subsets, this approach facilitates the identification of a minimal set of inefficient DMUs. This is crucial in terms of maintaining the discriminatory power of the model, especially considering the balance between the number of DMUs and the number of variables. Unlike traditional forward benchmarking that expands the DMU set, this study introduced a backward analysis, beginning with the full set and iteratively narrowing down toward the least efficient units. This approach is more realistic, as it supports gradual, data - driven improvements through comparisons with the nearest efficient benchmarks. It also provides more attainable target values for SDG 4 indicators a critical feature for policy implementation in countries facing larger gaps in performance.

The findings carry significant implications for benchmarking public policies in the area of sustainable development and education. In particular, they contribute to the policy discourse by offering a data-based framework for evaluating national education systems, including those of non-EU countries. By identifying nations with exemplary education policies, the analysis provides potential models for designing more effective systems, with attention to the broader societal implications of education-such as social equity, economic growth, and long-term sustainability. Furthermore, establishing a framework for monitoring SDG 4 implementation encourages countries to expand the scope of their national education policies. The inclusion of SDG 4 benchmarks introduces a key instrument not only for increasing accountability but also for fostering innovation and the development of tailored national tools in education policy. To achieve a comprehensive understanding of SDG 4 implementation, especially as promoted by the European Commission, it is necessary to replace static monitoring approaches with dynamic, iterative evaluation systems.

Finally, while the model used in this study focuses on a limited number of variables, this represents both a limitation and an opportunity. Future research would benefit from the inclusion of a broader range of qualitative and contextual factors, which would enhance the credibility and relevance of the findings.

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